

Measuring the level of self-awareness among faculty members in universities: demographic factors

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to measure the level of self-awareness among university faculty members, considering various demographic variables such as gender, academic specializations, and experience. The research was conducted on a sample of faculty members from four universities in Jordan and the United Arab Emirates (UAE): two from Jordan and two from the UAE. A sample of 172 faculty members was selected using an appropriate non-probability sampling technique. The researchers invited the entire study sample to participate in the self-awareness scale (SAS), developed using a translated Arabic version. The study found that the level of self-awareness among the sample was moderately average, with a mean score of 3.54. Additionally, according to the survey, there were no discernible gender disparities in self-awareness among university faculty members. However, there were statistically significant differences among faculty members in the sub-dimensions of realistic caution and self-reflection based on the experience variable, favoring faculty members with 11 or more years of experience. Significant differences were also observed in realistic awareness and indifference to external cues among faculty members specializing in humanities and social sciences compared to those in other specializations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Proper self-awareness is considered a prerequisite for self-organization since it allows one to identify subjective performance gaps precisely. Hence, we can think of the process of self-awareness as a key for turning on or turning off self-organization [1]. University, as a social institution, seeks to achieve several educational objectives. Faculty members have a central role in achieving the targeted educational objectives. In order to be able to influence the students' behaviors and attitudes, a faculty member should have a better understanding of himself and respond to questions related to his interests and objectives, the difficulties he is facing with students, and the way through which he behaves to find a relationship with students and employees. Indeed, responding to those questions will lead him to take more steps forward in self-awareness [2].

Self-awareness is viewed as a complex multi-dimensional phenomenon that includes different subjective domains as well as natural outcomes, such as the feeling of authority, where an individual can think of his past and future and focus on emotions, ideas, personality traits, preferences, objectives, situations, perception, feelings, and intentions [3]. Self-awareness helps the individual to control the various confrontations and impulses. It promotes self-motivation and personal fitness, considered the most critical social and emotional skills distinguishing the most successful individuals in their social lives [4]. There is a relationship between self-awareness and the management of emotions, in that self-awareness is necessary for

managing and regulating emotions, the individual's ability to manage himself, his rational compassion, and his understanding of others [5]. Compassionate and emotional participation is based on self-awareness, as it depends on our ability to accept our feelings and how we think we can identify and comprehend other people's feelings [6].

Faculty members are viewed as the fundamental pillar for the university's success in performing various tasks related to scientific research, teaching, and other administrative tasks. They have the responsibility of promoting the university in the future. Indeed, their ability to recognize themselves and identify their internal capabilities, as well as their abilities to make decisions, are considered basic skills that they should develop to improve their self-awareness. Also, identifying the level of self-awareness among the faculty members contributes to determining the faculty member's awareness of their professional and scientific tasks and their ability to affect other colleagues.

More self-awareness benefits a faculty member in his relationship with his students, where he becomes more aware of consistency between standards, objectives, and current achievements [7]. Self-awareness helps a faculty member understand his values, ambitions, needs, strengths, and weaknesses, determining the behaviors that should be modified and changed. In this way, he will have several more choices that help him develop effective relationships with his students.

Self-awareness has the potential to generate internal power and self-confidence, accept self, and take responsibility for one's actions and choices [8]. This awareness also helps the faculty member build on his strengths and reduce his weaknesses, which, in turn, contributes to the management of the teaching hall; the high performance and its results are manifested in developing the students' power and focusing on it. Self-aware faculty members are better able to connect with their students on a personal level, which allows them to form stronger academic relationships, engage them in extracurricular activities, and motivate them to reach their goals; indeed, the most important factors leading to the success of students are related to their relationship with their faculty members [9].

Faculty members have various requirements and expectations during their work at the university. They manifest emotional responses towards the tasks delegated to them; they behave angrily while dealing with the students who act in a way that is unacceptable socially; they are concerned with implementing scientific research and being informed with all the new information in their specialty and feel disappointed or depressed concerning students' academic achievement, in addition to the emotions resulting from stressors of the daily activities related to family, friends, and domestic affairs. A faculty member who has self-awareness has the ability to reflect on his internal status, realize it, and be evident [10].

A lack of self-awareness among university faculty members can have several negative consequences, both for the faculty members themselves and the university community as a whole. For example, faculty members who lack self-awareness may need help understanding their teaching methods and their impact on students. This can result in ineffective teaching practices and lower student engagement and learning outcomes. Also, self-awareness is crucial for effective communication. Faculty members who need more self-awareness may need help communicating with students, colleagues, and administrators, leading to misunderstandings and conflicts. In addition, collaborative research and academic projects are expected in universities. Faculty members who need more self-awareness may find it challenging to work effectively with colleagues, decreasing the quality and quantity of research output.

The research question was, what is the level of self-awareness among a sample of faculty members in several universities in Jordan and the United Arab Emirates (UAE)? We tested the hypothesis that, controlling for gender, specialty, and years of experience, there would be no statistically significant variations in self-awareness levels among a cross-section of university faculty members in Jordan and the UAE ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The results and discussion section will discuss the research question and hypothesis.

The significance of this study rests in the fact that it uses faculty members' self-estimations to determine their level of self-awareness, and it uses those results to illuminate the skill of self-awareness and its function in constructing positive social interactions. As far as the researchers know, there needs to be more Arabic studies that address the relationships between these variables. The importance of investigating self-awareness and emotional participation among faculty members, which, in turn, contributes to promoting professional development and developing the appropriate counseling programs for them. Detecting the positive domains in personality, particularly the variable of self-awareness and paying more attention to the faculty members responsible for teaching the community members and participating in the professional development of most employees working in different institutions to introduce the counseling and training programs related to the research's variables among those with low self-awareness levels and providing the research for the scale of self-awareness and modifying it to be compatible with the Arabic environment.

The current research adopted the definition introduced by Abdel-Hadi and Al Bustami [11] for self-awareness, who defined it as the individual's level relating to the internal and external criteria in order to establish an objective view about capabilities, potentials, strengths, and weaknesses, in addition to reflecting about feedback and realistic explicit criticism and employing the information relevant to self for achieve

development. In addition, by reflecting on and making sense of one's everyday experiences, one can get insight into one's character, weaknesses in one's behavior and personality, and the degree to which one has succeeded in reaching their goals. Self-awareness is considered one of the components of emotional intelligence, as suggested by Mayer *et al.* [12] where self-awareness is represented by internal personal Intelligence and is considered the basic pillar of emotional intelligence, which encompasses the ability to realize and pay attention to emotions and feelings [13].

Al-Sadi [14] defined self-awareness as the individual's ability to identify his feelings, beliefs, and attitudes in the current moment to make decisions, solve problems, and consciously monitor his motives, attitudes, and ideas. Personal self-awareness influences the choices consumers make. The simplicity of developing preferences in private self-awareness leads individuals to be more inclined and capable of trusting their subjective preferences in decision-making [15].

Newen and Vogeley [16] distinguished between conceptual self-awareness and representational self-awareness, where conceptual self-awareness refers to the individual's ability to represent himself conceptually, including his mental cases; it is mainly concerned with the self and his mental experiences. However, representational self-awareness includes the individual's ability to build a mental model for self and others and the ability to identify autobiography; it explicitly includes the memories about self and conclusions about the experiences of others. Hanson [17] suggested that the first origins of self-awareness are attributed to Freud's theory about consciousness and unconsciousness, where Freud suggested that self-awareness is focused on unconsciousness and is difficult to reach. However, Adler [18] refused this theory and assumed that self-awareness requires transmitting ideas from unconsciousness to consciousness, representing a continuous process of learning and transferring from mystery to clear understanding.

Based on the previous demonstration of self-awareness, scholars and theorists widely agree that self-awareness is linked to an individual's capacity to recognize their ideas, feelings, emotions, mental states, actions, and sayings. This ability enables them to identify their strengths and weaknesses. Indeed, these domains should be acknowledged by a faculty member, considering their position and social role.

A research at the University of Al Arish determined how gender and years of experience affect the degree to which faculty members and their assistants are psychologically empowered, self-aware, and emotionally engaged [19]. The results showed when it came to psychological empowerment, self-awareness, and emotional engagement, gender did not play a significant role. However, when it came to years of experience, there were significant differences, favoring those with more experience. Both self-awareness and emotional engagement were found to correlate statistically significantly with psychological empowerment.

Ghali [20] performed research to elucidate the interplay between psychological agency, self-awareness, social security, and the correlation between the variables above and psychological well-being. The study's variables were shown to be positively related to one another in a statistically meaningful way. The results showed that when controlling for gender, education level, and years of experience, there were no discernible variations in psychological empowerment, self-awareness, or social security.

Condon [21] researched how much self-awareness and other forms of emotional intelligence aid healthcare center managers in their leadership roles. Participants noted an increase in their awareness of themselves. Further, they were behaving differently and that their interactions with others were improving.

Titrek and Celik [22] surveyed a group of school administrators to learn more about their level of self-awareness and proficiency in transformational leadership techniques. For these data, regression analysis was employed. Findings showed that self-awareness was a predictor of transformative leadership style shifts. The findings showed that different areas of transformational leadership (idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, inspiring motivation, and personalized consideration) changed self-awareness at different rates.

Pololi and Franke [23] conducted a study that aimed to implement a training program for the faculty members in the faculty of medicine in order to develop teaching skills centered around the students by integrating traditional teaching methods that focus on knowledge, skills, and attitudes, with the non-traditional teaching methods. The results revealed that the training course had an essential role in developing enthusiasm towards teaching and the mastery of teaching skills. The faculty members reported achieving significant improvements in the skills of self-awareness and the habits of lifelong learning. They reported having a significant benefit from the training program manifested in developing personal relationships.

Baumeister *et al.* [24] analyzed studies that focused on self-awareness, self-esteem, and the variables impacting these concepts, and whether there were causal and correlational relationships between the variables of (age, experience, social level, and economic level) and the level of self-awareness, self-efficacy, and self-esteem. The results revealed several factors affecting the level of self-awareness, including the individual's school history, work, social relationships, and personal traits. The results revealed that care patterns, leadership, and social relationships improved self-awareness and self-esteem.

Ioannidou-Koutselini and Patsalidou [25] highlighted that the European Commission outlines priorities to enhance the quality of teacher training programs in the European Union (EU), focusing on access

to essential knowledge and skills, coordinated education provision, a culture of reflective practice, elevating the teaching profession, and supporting professionalization. Within this framework, the RELEASE project adapted Cyprus's in-service training for teachers to meet their needs better. It aimed to enhance school principals' pedagogic role and promote teachers' development and self-regulated learning skills. The article explains how action research can help educators grow professionally by describing how conversations have shifted from isolation to teamwork and from distrust to self-awareness. The analysis empirically supports the reflective paradigm of teacher development, which separates major components.

Shealy *et al.* [26] administered a program at a pharmacy school with multiple campuses to raise faculty and preceptors' levels of self-awareness and confidence. The intervention entailed instruction in active learning and the Birkman method of self-evaluation. Both self-awareness and coaching confidence showed considerable gains in the baseline and post-intervention surveys and the follow-up. Longitudinal findings revealed a positive correlation between sufficient Birkman method training and enhanced professional relationship management for both faculty and preceptors. Adequate training also improved preceptors' confidence in handling personal relationships and stress. This Birkman method-based intervention provides a concentrated strategy for helping teachers develop self-awareness and self-confidence while they work with their pupils.

Vadivel *et al.* [27] explored various aspects of continuous professional development (CPD) for English as foreign language (EFL) teachers' professional growth through a survey of 83 teachers. The diverse sample revealed that, while teachers are proactive in CPD, optimal outcomes require shared experiences, reflective teaching, and a sense of community. The findings stress CPD's significance in meeting global educational standards and advocating for teacher development programs to enhance educational achievements. The analysis underscores teachers' confidence, rooted in their belief in CPD. It emphasizes the need for each EFL teacher to take charge of their professional development for improved teaching and student success.

Hadi and Gharaibeh [28] asserted that impacted by self-awareness, a predictor of self-regulation, academics work to control their emotions in service of their professional and societal responsibilities. The purpose of the 172-person study was to determine if self-awareness is a predictor of emotional control issues. Lower levels of non-acceptance and more accessible goal-directed behavior were associated with higher levels of self-awareness (self-critical and desire for realistic awareness), according to results from the emotional regulation difficulties scale (ERDS) and the self-awareness scale (SAS). Problems with impulse control, difficulty setting and achieving goals, and overall levels of non-acceptance were all associated with increased levels of self-awareness (reflection). Academics at universities should develop self-awareness and emotional regulation skills to keep their emotions in check. In contrast, they work to interact with and regulate their tasks. The study underscores the need for further research on emotional regulation difficulties and their associations with other variables.

Based on the results of Abdillah *et al.* [29], self-regulation, self-evaluation, and self-efficacy are known to significantly impact employability ($F=134.28$ and $\text{sig}=.000$) when analyzed. At the .000, .001, and .000 significance levels, respectively, each independent variable—self-regulation, self-evaluation, and self-efficacy—substantially impacts employability. Results show that characteristics like self-regulation, self-evaluation, and self-efficacy—which come from within—are powerful enough to boost employability. This leads us to believe that vocational students' employability is affected by several external variables, but internal characteristics also play a significant role.

Based on the results of previous studies, we concluded that self-awareness plays a crucial role in individuals' success in social interaction. This is evident as self-awareness is closely linked to enthusiasm, developing relationships with others, self-regulation, self-acceptance, leadership, and administrative skills. Indeed, these findings emphasize the necessity of conducting field research to explore the level of self-awareness among the university faculty members. In contrast to earlier studies, this one aims to quantify faculty members' self-awareness and examine how demographic factors like gender, education level, area of expertise, and years of experience influence this attribute.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The researchers used the analytical descriptive approach on a sample of 172 faculty members from four universities (two universities in Jordan and two universities in the UAE), where the sample individuals were selected using convenient sampling. A similar approach was used by Baba *et al.* [30] in which the views of full-time faculty members at a handful of universities in northern India regarding the transformational leadership and emotional intelligence of their respective deans were investigated. The researchers invited the entire study sample to participate in the SAS developed by Ashley [1], using a translated Arabic version. The scale was distributed by using the electronic questionnaire designed on Google Forms.

2.1. Content validity

The content validity for the scale of self-awareness was verified by introducing the scale with its primary image to eight faculty members in the Department of Psychology and (Measurement and Evaluation) in different universities in Jordan and the UAE to voice their opinions on the items' content validity and scale membership, compatibility to assess the intended constructs, clarity level, and suggesting suitable revisions. The items were deemed legitimate when a consensus of 85% was reached. Some items were eliminated, and others were reworded to clarify them based on the arbitrators' assessments. In order to determine whether the substance and items of the scale were genuine, the researcher looked into the arbitrators' opinions and how they were changed. The contents of the scale were balanced after the necessary alterations, which indicates that the scale is face valid.

2.2. The validity of internal consistency

By determining the item's association with its corresponding dimension, we were able to confirm the construct validity indications, as illustrated in Tables 1 and 2. Table 1 reveals that all the values of correction coefficients for the dimension of "self-criticism" were statistically significant at (.01) and (.05) and that all the values of correction coefficients for the dimension of "the desire of realistic self-awareness" were statistically significant at (.01). The results also revealed that all the values of correction coefficients for the dimension of "indifference to external cues" were statistically significant at (.01) and (.05) and that all the values of correction coefficients for the dimension of "self-reflection" were statistically significant at (.01). Therefore, all the items are distinctive and measure the same characteristics; thus, the scale of self-awareness consisted of 62 items distributed to four main dimensions.

2.3. The reliability of the study scale

The scale's reliability was verified by calculating the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, as illustrated in Table 2. The table displays the Cronbach alpha values for the sub-dimensions of the emotion-regulation scale, ranging from .605 to .844. Additionally, the overall reliability coefficient of the scale was determined through Cronbach alpha. It was found to be .886, considered acceptable for the current study.

Table 1. Correlation coefficients of the paragraph with overall degree for each domain of the scale

Self-criticism		The desire for realistic self-awareness		Indifference to external cues		Self-reflection	
#	Correlation coefficient with the dimension	#	Correlation coefficient with the dimension	#	Correlation coefficient with the dimension	#	Correlation coefficient with the dimension
21	.375**	12	.345**	38	.395**	36	.819**
26	.402**	1	.395**	15	.555**	20	.809**
34	.788**	17	.461**	31	.464**	59	.531**
13	.786**	18	.196**	57	.260**	56	.814**
6	.534**	45	.518**	47	.351**	25	.806**
24	.779**	10	.374**	35	.461**	28	.473**
41	.166*	44	.252**	53	.552**	51	.829**
27	.282**	11	.811**	49	.610**	9	.332**
30	.298**	37	.275**	62	.178*	23	.315**
29	.458**	52	.810**	60	.253**	58	.779**
14	.516**	8	.390**	54	.243**	61	.296**
2	.737**	43	.442**			50	.499**
16	.743**	42	.251**			48	.468**
4	.495**	3	.598**				
46	.548**	32	.438**				
19	.772**	22	.662**				
39	.374**	7	.571**				
		5	.488**				
		40	.257**				
		55	.802**				
		33	.813**				

**statistically significant at (.01), *significance level (.05)

Table 2. The correlation coefficient of the items of the scale of self-awareness using the Cronbach alpha test

The dimensions of the scale of self-awareness	Correlation coefficient using Cronbach alpha
Self-criticism	.844
The desire for realistic self-awareness	.844
Indifference to external cues	.605
Self-reflection	.835
Total score	.886

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

The study sample included 172 faculty members. Taken from Philadelphia University (n=127, 74%), the Arab Open University - Jordan Branch (n=28, 16%), and Al Falah University - Dubai (n=17, 10%). The sample was chosen by the simple random method. The scale was distributed and sent via e-mail. Faculty members who speak Arabic were chosen because the scale items have been translated into Arabic. Table 3 shows the frequencies and percentages of the study sample by gender, years of experience, educational qualification, and specialty.

Table 3. The distribution of the sample individuals according to the demographic variables

Variable	Frequency	%	
Gender	Male	102	59.3
	Female	70	40.7
	Total	172	100.0
Years of experience	1-5 years	50	29.1
	6-10 years	45	26.2
	11-15 years	45	26.2
	16 years or more	32	18.6
	Total	172	100.0
Educational qualification	Ph.D.	135	78.5
	Master	37	21.5
	Total	172	100.0
University	Arab Open University	28	16.3
	Philadelphia University	127	73.8
	Al-Falah University	17	9.9
	Total	172	100.0
Specialty	Scientific sciences	82	47.7
	Human sciences	90	52.3
	Total	172	100.0

3.1.1. The results relate to the first question

To answer the question, "What is the level of self-awareness among faculty members in universities?" the means and standard deviations were computed to determine the level of self-awareness among university faculty members. Table 4 shows the results. According to the table, self-awareness scores varied from 2.93 to 4.16 on a very low to very high; a medium degree of general self-awareness was indicated by a score of 3.54. At a very high level, the need for realistic self-awareness ranked first, with a mean of 4.16 and a standard deviation of .40. Positioned second with an excellent standard deviation of .58 and a mean of 3.75, the self-reflection dimension was also high-level. With a mean of 2.93 and a standard deviation of .35, the dimension of indifference for external cues occupied the fourth spot. In contrast, the dimension of self-criticism occupied the third place with a standard deviation of .53, indicating a medium level.

Table 4. Means and standard deviations of the level of self-awareness

Self-awareness	Mean	SD	Order	Level
The desire for realistic self-awareness	4.16	.40	1	High
Self-reflection	3.75	.58	2	High
Self-criticism	3.29	.53	3	Medium
indifference to external cues	2.93	.35	4	Medium
Total	3.54	.30		Medium

3.1.2. The results relating to the study hypothesis

Based on the data in Table 5, we can see that university faculty members' levels of self-awareness vary according to gender (male/female), years of experience, specialty, and the interaction of these factors. To test this hypothesis, we ran a multiple analysis of co-variance (MANCOVA). Table 5 shows that when controlling for gender, there are no significant differences in the levels of self-awareness along the dimensions of self-criticism, desire for self-awareness, indifference to external cues, self-reflection, and total scale (f-values of 1.79, .220, .545, .091, and 1.162, respectively) ($p > .05$). All three levels of self-awareness (desire for self-awareness, self-reflection, and total self-awareness) were shown to be significantly different when controlling for years of experience (f-values of 4.556, 6.556, and 3.240, respectively; p-values of .05). Using Scheffe's test for post-comparisons, the researcher determined that the years of experience account for

most of the variation in these variables, with those with 16 years or more of experience being the most significantly different from those with 11–15 years.

Table 5. Results of (MANCOVA) on all domains of the scale according to variables

Independent variables		Value	Degree of freedom	Mean square	F-value	Sig. level
Gender (Hotelling Trace=.17) at a significance level (.814)	Self-criticism	.338	1	.338	1.790	.183
	The desire for realistic self-awareness	.020	1	.020	.220	.640
	Indifference to external cues	0.032	1	.032	.545	.462
	Self-reflection	0.014	1	.014	.091	.763
	Self-awareness (total)	0.064	1	.064	1.162	.283
Experience (Wilks Lambda=.714) at a significance level (*.00)	Self-criticism	0.906	3	.302	1.599	.193
	The desire for realistic self-awareness	1.256	3	.419	4.556	.005*
	Indifference to external cues	.415	3	.138	2.349	.075
	Self-reflection	2.873	3	.958	6.068	.001*
	Self-awareness (total)	.539	3	.180	3.240	.024*
Specialty (Hotelling Trace=.192) at a significance level (*.00)	Self-criticism	.725	1	.725	3.838	.052
	The desire for realistic self-awareness	.468	1	.468	5.100	.026*
	Indifference to external cues	.297	1	.297	5.039	.026*
	Self-reflection	.480	1	.480	3.038	.084
	Self-awareness (total)	.300	1	.300	5.404	.022*
Gender×experience×specialty (Wilks Lambda=.042) at a significance level (*.00)	Self-criticism	14.266	31	.460	2.437	.000
	The desire for realistic self-awareness	8.889	31	.287	3.121	.000
	Indifference to external cues	7.586	31	.245	4.155	.000
	Self-reflection	25.162	31	.812	5.142	.000
	Self-awareness (total)	5.503	31	.178	3.201	.000
Error	Self-criticism	24.931	132	.189		
	The desire for realistic self-awareness	12.126	132	.092		
	Indifference to external cues	7.775	132	.059		
	Self-reflection	20.835	132	.158		
	Self-awareness (total)	7.319	132	.055		
Total	Self-criticism	1907.125	172			
	The desire for realistic self-awareness	2999.780	172			
	Indifference to external cues	1492.653	172			
	Self-reflection	2482.059	172			
	Self-awareness (total)	2174.976	172			
Corrected total	Self-criticism	48.846	171			
	Desire for realistic self-awareness	27.542	171			
	Indifference to external cues	20.607	171			
	Self-reflection	56.959	171			
	Self-awareness (total)	15.622	171			

The results showed that the level of self-criticism and the indifference to external cues were not significantly different according to the years of experience variable (f-values of 1.599 and 2.349, respectively) and that none of these values were statistically significant at the .05 level. At the .05 significance level, the results showed that the level of self-awareness and its dimensions (desire for self-awareness, self-reflection, indifference to external cues, and total scale) were not significantly different when the years of specialty variable were considered. The corresponding f-values were 3.838, 5.100, and 5.039, respectively. The researcher employed a t-test to determine the origin of the differences. Findings favored the social and human sciences as the field from which disparities originated.

The results showed that the amount of self-criticism and self-reflection was not significantly different when the specialization variable was considered (f-value=3.038; p=.05). According to Table 5, there are variations in the levels of self-criticism, self-awareness desire, self-reflection, total scale, and apathy toward external cues based on gender and specialty. In that order, their interplay produced statistically significant values for (f) at (2.437, 3.121, 4.155, 5.142, 3.201).

3.2. Discussion

The mean general self-consciousness score was 3.54 out of 5, indicating a moderate level of awareness. The first place went to the dimension of “the desire for realistic self-awareness,” which had a high average mean score of 4.16. The second place went to the dimension of “self-reflection,” which also had a very high score of 3.75. Rounding out the top three was the dimension of “self-criticism,” with a mean of 3.29, a medium level; and “indifference to external cues,” ranked last, again a medium level, with a mean of 2.93. This study's findings were in agreement with previous study [11]. Results showed that the Abu Dhabi University faculty members had a medium level of self-awareness. Emotional intelligence is a critical

component in [30]. A strong and direct correlation was shown between the emotional intelligence of leaders and the faculty members' perceptions of transformational leadership styles.

A lack of statistically significant differences in self-awareness levels across genders was found across all dimensions of self-awareness (self-criticism, desire for self-awareness, indifference to external cues, self-reflection, and total scale). Based on the findings, it was determined that several studies [11], [14], [19] whereby it was found that the degree of self-awareness associated with gender does not differ statistically. However, this study's findings were at odds with those of Al-Sadi [14] because the sample included social workers employed by the Ministry of Social Development.

There were significant variations in the levels of self-awareness, self-reflection, and overall scale when comparing groups with 16 and 11–15 years of experience, respectively, as attributed to the years of experience variable. This finding aligns with previous study [19], which also found noticeable disparities based on experience level, favoring individuals with more years of expertise. According to the results, there are considerable variances among the faculty members regarding educational qualification, specialty, and years of experience, contrary to what was found in other study [11].

According to the results, the amount of self-criticism and apathy toward outside signals attributed to the experience variable did not differ significantly. In contrast to the present study, which examined university faculty members' levels of self-awareness about demographic variables like gender, experience, and specialty, Baumeister *et al.* [24] sought to determine the nature of the relationships between age, socioeconomic status, self-efficacy, self-esteem, and other variables by reviewing research on the subject. Furthermore, this study's findings indicate that specialists in the social and human sciences have a higher level of self-awareness and its three dimensions—desire for self-awareness, indifference to external cues, and total scale—compared to those in other fields. According to the findings, the degree of self-criticism and self-reflection is unaffected by the specialized variable. Last but not least, the data showed that gender, experience, specialty, and the interplay between these factors contribute to unique levels of self-criticism, realistic self-awareness desires, indifference to external cues, self-reflection, and total scale. Sutton [31] demonstrated that various variables had distinct effects on self-awareness, and our study confirms those findings. Regression of outcomes against self-awareness measures revealed that ruminating predicted lower benefits and higher costs, mindfulness indicated increased proactivity and costs, while self-reflection and insight predicted excellent results.

These results have real-world educational policy and practice implications, such as the need for more faculty self-awareness training programs and seminars. Provide faculty members with individualized workshops and counseling sessions and enhanced encouragement to engage in professional development and ongoing education to aid in their professional growth and attaining professional goals. Furthermore, establishing online study groups or forums to promote scientific communication and debate encourages sharing information and ideas.

4. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the level of self-awareness among university faculty members, considering various demographic variables such as gender, academic specialty, and experience. The study's sample comprised faculty members from four universities, with two located in Jordan and two in the United Arab Emirates. These universities collectively formed the basis for gathering data on self-awareness among faculty members.

In the light of the results, the study recommended the following. First, providing training programs and workshops to enhance self-awareness among faculty members. These programs could include the skills of self-thinking, ability analysis, personal skills, and developing personal and professional objectives and second, providing individual support and guidance to the faculty members in the domains of self-development and achievement of professional objectives, where the provided guidance may include individual workshops, guidance sessions, and more encouragement to faculty members to participate in the opportunities of continuous learning and professional programs. Third, scientific interactions and discussions can be achieved by making electronic forums or study groups to exchange knowledge and ideas. Finally, establishing and enhancing a supportive environment improves the level of self-awareness among the faculty members. This can be achieved by developing social and psychological support programs, providing opportunities for communication with colleagues and exchanging experiences, and encouraging participation in scientific seminars and conferences.

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